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Dear Kari,
Dear Kari,

Thank you for your straight letter which reached me in Muscat. Of course if we had known in December that the dollar was going to devalue I could have raised money for DD in 1973, now although I am making enquiries it is basically too late since Dec-Jan is the normal closing date for the few sources available. So if a partial season is possible on your sources it would be very worthwhile, but I'll keep you informed.

I saw Bacerzadeh in Tehran who seemed enthusiastic and in good form. Certainly a few weeks survey after Yahya should well be feasible, and I hope that would help Martha; but he just could not clear anything for survey before Yahya as he is desperately busy at the moment— He tells me that he often does not get to see telegrams for a week. This survey for her could not extend beyond the end of September since I take up the job of Director of Antiquities of Oman on October 1. In that capacity I will be responsible for granting research permits and will welcome Harvard research in Oman.

I have received the DD drawings which in most cases are very nice. Thank you.— A problem has arisen over the shipment of DD finds of 1971. They were delivered almost a year ago, at that time the English handlers and I believed that the bill had been prepaid in Tehran. It has turned out that since that either the bill was not paid in Tehran or there is some hang up there. Perhaps you could clarify this. Incidentally the bill \$55 is too high. In future it would be more economical to ship finds to Harvard and then have them brought to the U.K.

Well I hope the dollar revalues or that you otherwise solve your financial problems—the hydrological and soils work sound as if they will be v. worthwhile.

best wishes,